

EXPERIMENTING WITH GENETIC ALGORITHM ON THE PALLET LOADING PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT

Metaheuristic techniques are being increasingly used to get reasonably good solutions for combinatorially explosive problems. Yet these methods have not been tried on the Pallet Loading Problem, although it is of significant practical importance. This is because of the fact that, as of date, there is no convenient way - other than graphical - to represent solutions to the problem. In this paper, we discuss a method for representing the solutions and apply Genetic Algorithm to solve the Pallet Loading Problem. Preliminary results reported here are quite encouraging.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metaheuristic methods like tabu search and genetic algorithm are increasingly becoming popular to obtain 'reasonably good' solutions for combinatorially explosive problems. Applications abound in areas like scheduling, flowshop sequencing and routing problems [Reeves 1993]. The Pallet Loading Problem (PLP) under consideration has immense practical significance and is known to be NP-Complete [Dowland 1987]. In PLP, the objective is to place as many identical rectangular pieces as possible on a rectangular pallet with the edges of the pieces parallel to the edges of the pallet. Existing methods [Dowland 1987, Bhattacharya et al. 1997] that output optimal solutions can solve problems of moderate size. For larger problems, one has to rely on heuristic techniques to get 'good' solutions. Yet, the metaheuristic techniques that have met with success in other areas, could not be tried on this problem due to lack of any convenient mechanism to represent the solutions to the problem. [Cheng et al. 1994] and [Dowland & Dowland 1992] are excellent survey papers that summarize past approaches to solve the PLP.

This paper attempts to use the concept of *Maximal Breadth Filling Sequence* introduced in [Bhattacharya et al. 1997] to represent solutions to PLP. Once we know the technique for representing the solutions, metaheuristics can now be applied on this problem. We have experimented with Genetic Algorithm and the initial results reported here are quite encouraging.

Section 2 introduces the problem and discusses the way of representing its solutions.

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Section 3 outlines our Genetic Algorithm (GA) formulation. Section 4 gives results obtained with GA on problems for which optimal solutions are known. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 THE PROBLEM AND REPRESENTATION OF ITS SOLUTIONS

2.1 THE PROBLEM AND ASSOCIATED TERMINOLOGY

In the pallet loading problem (PLP), we are given one rectangular pallet of length X units and breadth Y units, $X \geq Y$, and an infinite supply of rectangular pieces each of length a units and breadth b units, $a \geq b$, $a \leq X$, $b \leq Y$. Without loss of generality, we consider the numbers X , Y , a and b to be integers. The objective is to find a layout for placing as many non-overlapping pieces as possible on the pallet, with the edges of the pieces parallel to the edges of the pallet. Thus the only rotation allowed to a piece is by 90 degrees. We get the same problem if we disallow rotation and consider two types of rectangular pieces, each with infinite supply, having dimensions a by b and b by a . Henceforth, an a by b piece will be referred to as a H-piece and a b by a piece, a V-piece. $\lfloor XY/ab \rfloor$ is an upper bound on the number of pieces that can be laid on the pallet, and will be used as a measure for the size of the problem. Throughout the paper, the top left corner of the pallet will be assumed to be at length 0 with length increasing downwards, and at breadth 0 with breadth increasing to the right. A solution to the problem is defined as an arrangement of H and V pieces on the pallet such that no more pieces can be placed on the pallet without disturbing the arrangement.

The concept of MBFS introduced in [Bhattacharya et al. 1997] is as follows. Let (n, m) be an ordered pair of non-negative integers such that

$$0 \leq Y - n * a - m * b < b.$$

Given one such ordered pair (n, m) , consider the sequence of m H-pieces and n V-pieces with all V-pieces placed before all H-pieces. Each such sequence represents a possible combination of H and/or V pieces that can be placed on the pallet in a row to maximally fill up the breadth of the pallet. Each such sequence, W_i , is called an MBFS, *maximal breadth filling sequence*. For a given triplet (Y, a, b) with $a \geq b$, the number M of MBFSs is $\lfloor Y/a \rfloor + 1$. These M MBFSs represent possible combinations of H and V-pieces to maximally fill up the breadth of the pallet.

For each of the MBFS W_i constructed as above, *B-Loss*, BL_i given by

$$BL_i = Y - \sum w_j, \quad w_j \text{ is the breadth of the } j\text{th piece in } W_i, \quad 1 \leq j \leq K_i.$$

where K_i is the cardinality of W_i , i.e., the number of pieces in the MBFS W_i .

When the pieces in W_i are placed along the breadth of a pallet starting from the left edge, BL_i represents the loss along the breadth of the pallet. Clearly, BL_i can range from 0 to $b-1$.

From now on, we will assume the M MBFSs corresponding to the triplet (Y, a, b) of the given problem (X, Y, a, b) to form an ordered list arranged firstly on non-decreasing order of B-Loss and secondly on non-increasing order of the cardinality of the MBFSs. That is, for two MBFS W_i and W_j in the ordered list, $i < j$, we have $BL_i \leq BL_j$; if $BL_i = BL_j$, then $K_i \geq K_j$.

Example 1 : Consider the problem of placing 7 by 3 pieces on a pallet of size 13 by 11, i.e., $X = 13$, $Y = 11$, $a = 7$ and $b = 3$. The 7 by 3 piece is the H-piece and the 3 by 7 piece is the V-piece. The ordered list of MBFSs is

W_1	V H	with $BL_1 = 1$
W_2	H H H	with $BL_2 = 2$

□

2.2 REPRESENTING SOLUTION TO PLP

Consider those solutions of a given problem where the pieces placed on the pallet have been pushed towards the top edge of the pallet as far as possible without any overlap of pieces. The solutions need not be optimal. For any such solution, it can be shown that ([Bhattacharya et al. 1997]) at any point along the length of the pallet, the pieces placed between the left and right edges of the pallet belong to one of the MBFSs, or a subset of it, though may not be in the same order. Clearly, if at any point the pieces placed along the breadth is a subset of an MBFS, at no subsequent point can it be a complete MBFS since we have pushed the pieces as far to the top as possible.

The above result implies that a solution to PLP can be represented as a sequence of MBFSs. In other words, given a PLP (X, Y, a, b) and a feasible sequence of n MBFSs $p_1 p_2 \dots p_n$, it is possible to come up with an algorithm to get the layout of the pieces on the pallet.

Algorithm LayPieces

- Step 1 : Construct the M MBFSs, W_i and order them on BL_i and K_i
- Step 2 : Place the pieces corresponding to the MBFS W_{p_1} along the top edge of the pallet.
Set *DecisionPt* to the topmost bottom edge of the pieces placed.
- Step 3 : For each of the MBFSs p_i in the remaining sequence do
- Step 3A: Lay the pieces in W_{p_i} at *DecisionPt* in the following manner :

Assume there are $r (\geq 0)$ H-pieces in W_{pi} . Let $s (\geq 0)$ be the number of H-pieces on the pallet with top edge before *DecisionPt* but bottom edge beyond *DecisionPt*. $\text{Min}(r, s)$ of these H-pieces are retained on the pallet. If $s > r$, then the pieces retained are those r pieces with earliest top edges, the remaining $s-r$ H-pieces are withdrawn from the pallet. If $r > s$ then each of the $r-s$ H-pieces will be placed with their top edges at *DecisionPt*. Any piece for which the bottom edge overshoots the bottom edge of the pallet are also withdrawn which implies that only a subset of W_{pi} could be assigned. Positions for the top edges of the V-pieces in W_{pi} are assigned in a similar manner.

Step 3B: Set *DecisionPt* to the topmost bottom edge of the pieces placed in Step 3A.

Example 2 : Consider the problem given in Example 1 and the MBFS sequence 1211. This accommodates five pieces with the following layout.

- Number by the side of a state is the *DecisionPt*
- Irrecoverable waste area till *DecisionPt* is blackened.

It may be noted that this sequence 1211 is a complete solution but not optimal. For this problem the optimal sequence is 11211 accommodating six pieces on the pallet.

3 GENETIC ALGORITHM FORMULATION

Genetic algorithm has been tried on various combinatorial optimization problems [Reeves 1993]. Detail of genetic algorithm can be obtained in [Goldberg 1989]. This is the first attempt to use the scheme on the pallet loading problem.

The starting point of the scheme is the formation of an initial population of individuals (chromosomes), each of which represents a feasible solution to the original problem. In our case, each chromosome is a sequence of MBFSs that maximally fills up the pallet. We first form M (the number of MBFSs) chromosomes, the i th chromosome being a sequence of MBFS i only. The size of the initial population is taken as a prespecified (and tunable) multiple of the average length of the above M chromosomes. The remaining chromosomes are formed with the probability of an MBFS i being selected next in the sequence depending on the fitness of the chromosome which is a sequence of MBFS i only. The fitness of a chromosome is defined by the number of pieces that the chromosome accommodates on the pallet. Obviously the chromosomes can be of different lengths. In any population the best (worst) chromosome is one with highest (lowest) fitness value. Ties are resolved on the basis of the last *DecisionPt* of the chromosome - lower the last *DecisionPt*, better is the chromosome.

The next step in the scheme is to select two parents from the population for mating. The first parent is chosen using the probability distribution of the fitness values of the chromosomes. The second parent is chosen randomly from among those chromosomes which differ from the first parent in at least two positions within the length that is minimum of the lengths of the chromosomes under consideration. If no such second parent can be found the algorithm terminates and the best chromosome of the current population is declared as the solution of the problem. In this situation, we say that the system has saturated.

The only genetic operator used in our formulation is the one-point crossover operator. The crossover point is chosen randomly in the region between the first and last differing positions of the parents. Two offsprings result, one with left part of first parent and right part of the second parent and vice versa. It may be noted that an offspring produced in this manner may not represent a feasible solution. It has now to be modified to be a feasible solution. If the resulting MBFS sequence overshoots the pallet edge, the tail of it is appropriately curtailed to be accommodated within the pallet. On the other hand, if any length of the pallet remains uncovered, it is filled up by trying out the MBFSs in order of their B-losses. The procedure terminates when the difference between the next *DecisionPt* and the bottom edge of pallet is less than b . The better of the two offsprings generated by the crossover is retained. It replaces the worst chromosome of the current population. Thus the next generation with all but one individuals of the previous generation and the best offspring obtained by crossover.

This process of moving from generation to generation continues until one of the following three things happen :

- (a) the system saturates (explained above).
- (b) the system has gone through a pre-specified (and tunable) number of generations.
- (c) the best solution obtained so far is the same as the theoretical limit on the number of pieces that can be placed on the effective area of the pallet. Note that the effective breadth of the pallet is the breadth of the pallet minus the minimum B-loss among the MBFSs. The effective length of the pallet can be obtained in a similar manner, and the effective area of the pallet calculated.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Experiments with the above genetic algorithm scheme were carried out on a 100 MHz Pentium PC. Compact model of Borland C version 3.1 was used. Runs for the exact algorithm ([Bhattacharya et al. 1997]) were taken on the same Pentium machine. The problems on which the algorithm was tried were taken from [Bhattacharya et al. 1997]. These are

Set I The following isolated problems from the literature

Dowsland's problems : (22, 16, 5, 3), (30, 22, 7, 4), (46, 34, 11, 6), (50, 36, 11, 7), (53, 51, 9, 7), (63, 60, 11, 8), (76, 73, 13, 10), (86, 82, 15, 11); and

Nelißen's problems : (3750, 3063, 646, 375), (40, 33, 7, 4), (1200, 800, 176, 135), (34, 23, 5, 4).

Set II : One thousand problems, each satisfying the following constraints :

$$X = 1200; \quad Y = 1000; \quad 1 \leq a/b \leq 4; \quad 1 \leq XY/ab \leq 50;$$

Set III : One thousand problems, each satisfying the following constraints :

$$X = 1100; \quad Y = 1100; \quad 1 \leq a/b \leq 4; \quad 1 \leq XY/ab \leq 50;$$

In our implementation of the genetic algorithm, after some initial experiments, we set the population size to six times the average length of the M MBFS sequences each of which was a feasible repetition of only one of the MBFSs. The maximum number of generations allowed was six hundred. While fixing these parameters, the trade off was between number of problems solved optimally and the time taken.

Set I Results: All the problems in Set I were solved optimally. The total time taken for the eight Dowsland's problems was 0.75 seconds while that for the four Nelißen's problems was 1.15 seconds. The total time taken to solve all the twelve problems by the exact algorithm was 5.54 seconds.

Set II and Set III Results: To study the results, the problems in each set have been split into five groups based on the problem size. Performance of the algorithm on these

problems are summarized in Tables 1 and 2. All the execution times are given in seconds.

Table No. 1 : Genetic Algorithm on Set II Problems

Problem Size		1-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	50-100
No. of Problems		185	204	197	199	215	1000
Time Taken (By Exact algorithm)	Avg	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.13	0.92	2.23
	s.d.	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.15	1.64	0.84
	Max	0.05	0.05	0.22	0.77	12.20	12.20
Time Taken (By Genetic algorithm)	Avg	0.01	0.03	0.07	0.13	0.18	0.09
	s.d.	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.10	0.11	0.10
	Max	0.22	0.22	0.27	0.38	0.38	0.38
Optimally Solved		184	196	190	178	187	935
Missing optimal by one piece		1	8	7	21	28	65

Table No. 2 : Genetic Algorithm on Set III Problems

Problem Size		1-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	50-100
No. of Problems		179	199	216	204	202	1000
Time Taken (By Exact algorithm)	Avg	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.21	1.40	0.33
	s.d.	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.28	3.33	1.60
	Max	0.00	0.05	0.16	1.70	29.95	29.95
Time Taken (By Genetic algorithm)	Avg	0.02	0.05	0.11	0.14	0.20	0.11
	s.d.	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.10	0.10
	Max	0.22	0.27	0.27	0.33	0.38	0.38
Optimally Solved		175	193	210	172	169	919
Missing optimal by one piece		4	6	6	32	29	77
Missing optimal by two pieces		0	0	0	0	4	4

The following observations can be made on the basis of the experimental results :

- (i) Genetic Algorithm (GA) gave optimal solutions in 93% problems in set II and 92% in set III. In set II, the suboptimal solutions were only one piece away from the optimal solutions. However, in set III, there were four problems for which the GA solutions were two pieces away from the optimal.
- (ii) The average execution time is less than that of the Exact algorithm. More importantly, and quite expectedly, the standard deviations for the running times is low for the GA algorithm. 0.38 seconds seems to be the maximum time that GA would take on this problem with a maximum of six hundred generations and population size set to six times the average length of the M MBFS sequences.

Overall, the proposed GA scheme seems to be quite an acceptable trade off between time taken and quality of solution obtained.

5 CONCLUSION

We have discussed a mechanism for representing solutions to the Pallet Loading Problem, paving the way to apply metaheuristic techniques on this problem. As an example we have tried the Genetic Algorithm. The initial results reported are quite impressive. Currently, efforts are being made to improve upon the GA scheme and also to try out other techniques like Tabu Search. It would be interesting to see how these metaheuristic methods perform on the more generalized problem of Two-dimensional Rectangular Non-guillotine Cutting problem.

REFERENCES

1. [Bhattacharya et al. 1997] Subir Bhattacharya, Rahul Roy and Sumita Bhattacharya, "An Exact Depth-first Algorithm for the Pallet Loading Problem", *European Journal of Operational Research*, forthcoming.
2. [Cheng et al. 1994] C. H. Cheng, B. R. Feiring, and T. C. E. Cheng, "The Cutting Stock Problem - A Survey", *International Journal of Production Economics* 36(1994) 291-305.
3. [Dowsland & Dowsland 1992] K. A. Dowsland, and W. B. Dowsland, "Packing Problems", *European Journal of Operational Research* 56(1992) 2-14.
4. [Dowsland 1987] K. A. Dowsland, "The Three-dimensional Pallet Chart: An Analysis of the Factors Affecting the set of Feasible Layouts for a Class of Two-dimensional Packing Problems", *Journal of the Operational Research Society* 35(1984) 895-905.
5. [Goldberg 1989] D. E. Goldberg, "Genetic Algorithms in Search, Optimization, and Machine Learning", Addison-Wesley, Reading, Mass., 1989.
6. [Reeves 1993] Colin R. Reeves (Ed.), "Modern Heuristic Techniques for Combinatorial Problems", Orient Longman, 1993.